

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.2.2.3: International crises: armed conflict and emergency relief

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Project leader and contributors:

- Vigdis Vandvik (Vigdis.Vandvik@uib.no)

- Sonya Geange

Data curator(s):

- Vigdis Vandvik (Vigdis.Vandvik@uib.no)

- Ryoko Kawakami (r-kawakami@iges.or.jp)

Description

Section 3.2.2.3 assesses the role of international crises such as war and aid as drivers of biological invasions. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

TITLE: ("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND TOPIC: (war OR aid OR battle) AND TOPIC: (plant* OR animal* OR microbe* OR fish* OR organism* OR fung*)

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

- **Date:** November 2021

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

305 from literature search

Selection criteria:

Search 1: Searched with above terms, then refined by document type (review) excluding low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 2: Then excluded low relevant papers from Top 50 papers by experts' knowledge.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 2

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):

Number of papers reviewed: 37 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx